

TLC-ANALYSIS OF ANDIPAL IN CHEMICO-TOXICOLOGICAL STUDIES**Karimova Kh.D.****Zulfikarieva D.A.**

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Relevance. Chemico-toxicological laboratory diagnostics of poisoning with combined drugs requires methods that allow simultaneous detection of several active substances in biological material. One of such methods is thin-layer chromatography (TLC), which is characterized by simplicity, availability, and sufficient sensitivity. The object of the study is the drug Andipal, which contains: metamizole sodium, papaverine hydrochloride, phenobarbital, and dibazole. Poisoning cases with combined preparations are frequent, and multi-component drugs are difficult to identify in biological material. Therefore, it is important to develop a universal method for detecting combined drugs, in particular Andipal. TLC analysis is convenient both for detecting and for purifying and separating multi-component drugs from extracts obtained from biological material.

Purpose of the study: To develop a simple and affordable method for detecting Andipal in biological material using TLC.

Materials and methods: As the stationary phase, silica gel plates UV254 were used. Solvent systems:

1. butanol – acetic acid – water (4:1:5);
2. chloroform – acetone – ethanol (6:3:1).

Among many reagents tested for visualization of the zones of Andipal's components, the following optimal developers were selected: Marquis reagent or iodine vapors (metamizole, dibazole), Dragendorff reagent or ninhydrin (papaverine, dibazole), UV irradiation (phenobarbital, papaverine).

Results: Metamizole sodium. Rf: 0.35–0.40. Developer/detection: Marquis reagent, iodine vapors. Spot characteristics: violet coloration. Significance: a rapid screening test for the diagnosis of analgesic poisoning.

Papaverine hydrochloride. Rf: 0.50–0.55. Developer/detection: Dragendorff reagent. Spot characteristics: orange-brown coloration. Significance: reliable confirmation of papaverine among other alkaloids.

Phenobarbital. Rf: 0.65–0.70. Developer/detection: UV lamp (254 nm). Spot characteristics: bluish-green fluorescence. Significance: important marker in toxicological analysis in suspected sedative poisoning.

Dibazole. Rf: 0.75–0.80. Developer/detection: ninhydrin reagent. Spot characteristics: red-brown coloration. Significance: confirms the presence of dibazole in the formulation, facilitates comprehensive identification of Andipal.

TLC analysis of Andipal allows the simultaneous detection of all four active substances in a single sample. Different Rf values and spot color characteristics provide high selectivity of the method. Sensitivity ranges from 5 to 10 µg/spot, making the method suitable for toxicological purposes. Although TLC is a qualitative method and does not provide precise quantitative evaluation, it is indispensable at the stage of preliminary diagnostics of poisoning. For final identification, more specific instrumental methods are recommended (HPLC, GC-MS, spectrophotometry).

Conclusions: The TLC method is an accessible and effective approach for identifying the components of Andipal in biological samples. Each active ingredient has a characteristic Rf value and specific reaction to a developer. TLC results can be used for preliminary diagnostics and serve as the basis for further quantitative studies.